

Analysis 1

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMaker;
class Condition (ref="2") Group Generation (ref="1") ;
model PrevPerf = Generation Condition Generation*Condition / solution ddfm=satterthwaite;
random intercept Generation / subject=Group type=vc;
run;
```

Analysis 2

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMaker;
class Condition Group Generation ;
model WordsTrans = Generation Condition Generation*Condition / solution ddfm=satterthwaite;
random intercept Generation / subject=Group type=vc;
run;
```

Analysis 3

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMaker;
class ConditionORTH (ref="-1") Group GenerationORTH (ref="1");
model NextPerf = ConditionORTH GenerationORTH ConditionORTH*GenerationORTH WordsTransST
SumTransST SumRecalledST SumAdviceST / solution ddfm=satterthwaite;
random intercept GenerationORTH SumTransST SumRecalledST / subject=Group type=vc;
run;
```

Analysis 4

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMaker;
class ConditionORTH (ref="-1") Group GenerationORTH (ref="1");
model SumTrans = ConditionORTH GenerationORTH ConditionORTH*GenerationORTH PrevPerfST /
solution ddfm=satterthwaite;
random intercept GenerationORTH PrevPerfST / subject=Group type=vc;
run;
```

Analysis 5

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMaker;
```

```
class ConditionORTH (ref="-1") Group GenerationORTH (ref="1");  
  
model NTimesPerf = ConditionORTH GenerationORTH ConditionORTH*GenerationORTH SumTransST  
/ solution ddfm=satterthwaite;  
  
random intercept GenerationORTH / subject=Group type=vc;  
  
run;
```

Analysis 6

```
proc glimmix data=work.pastaH9;  
  
class Condition (ref="2") Generation (ref="1") Group inMU (ref="0");  
  
model NonRoutine = Condition Generation Condition*Generation inMU / solution  
ddfm=satterthwaite;  
  
random inMU / subject=Group type=vc;  
  
run;
```

Analysis 7

```
data pastaMakerMUFiltre;  
  
set work.pastaMakerMU;  
  
if RemoveTrans="1" then delete;  
  
run;  
  
proc glimmix data=work.pastaMakerMUFiltre;  
  
class Condition (ref="2") Generation (ref="1") Group;  
  
model Mu = Condition Generation Condition*Generation / solution ddfm=satterthwaite;  
  
random intercept Generation / subject=Group type=vc;  
  
run;
```